

FLAVONOID-LOADED CHITOSAN NANOGELS: PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND ANTIBACTERIAL EFFICACY AGAINST DIABETIC WOUND PATHOGENS

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Abstract

Diabetic wounds are among the most challenging complications of diabetes mellitus, often marked by delayed healing and persistent infections caused by resistant pathogens such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Conventional treatments are hindered by limited tissue penetration, increasing bacterial resistance, and poor patient compliance, creating a need for novel therapeutic approaches. Flavonoids, natural polyphenolic compounds, are known for their antimicrobial and wound-healing properties. This study aimed to overcome the limitations of traditional therapies by developing flavonoid-loaded chitosan nanogels and evaluating their physicochemical and antibacterial properties. The nanogels were formulated using ionotropic gelation, with particle characterization through dynamic light scattering and zeta potential analysis. The physicochemical assessment revealed suitable pH values (6.2–6.8), viscosities ranging from 825.12 ± 12.22 cP.

(luteolin) to 2110 ± 14 cP. (apigenin), and spreadability between 10.40 ± 0.21 g·cm/s (naringenin) and 13.10 ± 0.20 g·cm/s (kaempferol). Particle sizes ranged from 112.35 ± 1.55 nm (naringenin) to 412.8 ± 3.3 nm (luteolin), with zeta potentials varying from $+11.7 \pm 5.9$ mV (kaempferol) to $+37.4 \pm 2.1$ mV (luteolin), demonstrating good colloidal stability. Antibacterial testing revealed that luteolin nanogel exhibited the most potent broad-spectrum activity, with inhibition zones of 28.7 ± 0.50 mm against *S. aureus*, 26.9 ± 0.25 mm against *E. coli*, and 24 ± 0.25 mm against *P. aeruginosa*. MIC results showed apigenin (31.25 ± 0.25 µg/mL for *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*) and kaempferol (16 ± 0.25 µg/mL for *P. aeruginosa*) as the most effective growth inhibitors. MBC assays confirmed apigenin as the most bactericidal, requiring only 4 ± 0.25 µg/mL for *S. aureus*. In conclusion, flavonoid-loaded chitosan nanogels demonstrated strong antibacterial properties, with luteolin showing broad-spectrum inhibition, and apigenin and kaempferol exhibiting the lowest MIC and MBC values, positioning them as promising candidates for diabetic wound management.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetic wounds represent one of the most serious complications of diabetes mellitus, impacting millions of patients worldwide [1]. Delayed wound healing, compounded by persistent microbial colonization, frequently progresses to chronic ulcers, extended hospitalization, amputations, and a significantly diminished quality of life [2, 3]. Conventional systemic and topical therapies remain inadequate due to limited tissue penetration, escalating bacterial resistance, and poor patient adherence [4, 5]. These challenges emphasize the urgent demand for innovative, safe, and effective therapeutic modalities to combat wound-associated pathogens in diabetic patients [6, 7]. Flavonoids, a diverse group of naturally occurring polyphenolic compounds found in fruits and vegetables, are well known for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties [2, 8, 9]. Despite their therapeutic promise, clinical utilization is hampered by poor water solubility, low bioavailability, and instability under physiological environments. Nanotechnology-based delivery systems, particularly chitosan nanogels, have emerged as potential solutions [10]. Chitosan, a biodegradable and biocompatible polysaccharide, not only provides a cationic framework that stabilizes flavonoids but also contributes inherent antimicrobial and wound-healing benefits [11]. This synergistic platform offers a promising strategy to enhance flavonoid stability, enable efficient topical delivery, and augment antibacterial effects against multidrug-resistant pathogens frequently implicated in diabetic wound infections, including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [12, 13]. This study aimed to formulate and characterize flavonoid-loaded chitosan nanogels prepared via ionotropic gelation and to evaluate their physicochemical properties such as pH, viscosity, spreadability, particle size, and zeta potential. Antibacterial activity was further assessed

through minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC), and zone of inhibition assays. Results revealed notable differences among the flavonoids tested: luteolin nanogels displayed broad-spectrum potency, apigenin and kaempferol nanogels exhibited strong bactericidal activity against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*, whereas quercetin and naringenin produced moderate, strain-specific effects. These outcomes highlight the decisive role of flavonoid type in determining nanogel efficacy[2]. The significance of this work lies in its dual contribution advancing the therapeutic application of flavonoids through nanogel-based delivery and addressing a critical clinical challenge in diabetic wound care. By optimizing formulation parameters and demonstrating meaningful antibacterial potential, the study reinforces the relevance of nanotechnology-driven wound management strategies[14, 15]. Nonetheless, the current findings are limited to in vitro investigations, and additional in vivo and clinical studies are essential to confirm safety, pharmacological performance, and therapeutic utility.

METHODOLOGY

Preparation of Flavonoid Containing Chitosan Containing Nanogel by Solvent Evaporation Technique

Flavonoid-loaded chitosan nanogels were prepared by ionotropic gelation and subsequently incorporated into a topical gel base. Low-medium molecular weight chitosan (degree of deacetylation $\geq 80\%$) was dissolved in 0.1–1.0% v/v acetic acid to obtain a 1.0 mg/mL solution and adjusted to pH 4.8–5.2 with dilute NaOH. The flavonoid was pre-solubilized in a minimal volume of ethanol or PEG-400 (final cosolvent $\leq 5\%$ v/v) and introduced into the chitosan solution under magnetic stirring (600–800 rpm) for 10–15 min; where required, Tween-80 (0.02–0.05% w/v) or poloxamer F127 (0.05–0.2% w/v)

was added to aid dispersion. An aqueous sodium tripolyphosphate (TPP) solution (0.5 mg/mL) was then added dropwise (~1 mL/min) to the drug–chitosan mixture under continuous stirring, maintaining a chitosan:TPP mass ratio of 3:1 to 5:1 and a total volume ratio of approximately 1:4 to 1:6. Immediate opalescence indicated nanogel formation; stirring was continued for 30–60 min at room temperature to complete ionic crosslinking. The nanosuspension was purified by centrifugation (15,000–20,000 g, 10–20 min); the supernatant was retained for encapsulation calculations, and the pellet was gently re-dispersed in acetate buffer (pH ~5.5) or water, with one additional wash if necessary. In parallel, a topical gel base was prepared by hydrating Carbopol® 940 (0.5–1.0% w/w) in water containing 5–10% w/w propylene glycol under gentle stirring for 1–2 h, followed by gradual neutralization with triethanolamine to pH 6.0–6.5 to obtain a clear gel. The purified chitosan nanogel dispersion (typically ~100–300 nm, positively charged) was incorporated into the gel base at room temperature by geometric dilution to achieve a final drug content of 0.1–1% w/w, mixed until uniform, deaerated, and filled into light-resistant containers. This aqueous, ambient-temperature process avoids toxic crosslinkers and organic solvent residues while yielding a stable, cationic nanogel suitable for topical delivery of flavonoids [16].

Size and Zeta Potential of Flavonoid-Loaded Nanogels

Flavonoid-loaded nanogels/nanoparticles were characterized for hydrodynamic size by dynamic light scattering (DLS) and for surface charge by electrophoretic light scattering (zeta potential) at 25 °C. Fresh dispersions were prepared in filtered Milli-Q water or the intended buffer, gently vortexed, and diluted to achieve a stable, mid-range instrument count rate, avoiding visible turbidity or multiple scattering. Particulates were removed by brief low-speed centrifugation (\approx 3000 g, 5 min) or passage through a 0.45–0.22 μ m

syringe filter without concentrating the sample. DLS measurements used disposable low-volume polystyrene or quartz cuvettes; zeta measurements used folded capillary cells filled carefully to prevent bubbles. Dispersant refractive index and viscosity were set to the medium at 25 °C, with a 120 s equilibration before acquisition.

Hydrodynamic size was recorded in backscatter DLS ($\approx 173^\circ$) under automatic attenuation with ≥ 3 technical replicates per sample (≥ 10 –15 runs each). The Z-average diameter (cumulants mean) and polydispersity index (PDI) were reported from intensity-weighted data; number-weighted distributions were generated as needed. Data were accepted when correlograms showed stable baselines and intercepts, replicate %RSD for Z-average was $\leq 10\%$, and PDI ≤ 0.3 for monomodal systems.

Zeta potential was measured on the same dispersions using automatic voltage/attenuation with ≥ 3 replicates. Electrophoretic mobility was converted to zeta potential using the Smoluchowski model ($f(\kappa a) = 1.5$) for aqueous media, with alternative models and viscosity values applied when required by low ionic strength or increased viscosity. Results were expressed as mean \pm SD (mV). A certified latex/polystyrene standard and a blank dispersant were run in parallel to verify instrument performance and exclude background signal [17].

MIC, MBC and Zone of Inhibition of Flavonoids Containing Topical Nanogels

Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) were determined by broth microdilution. Fresh colonies of each test bacterium were suspended in sterile saline and adjusted to a 0.5 McFarland standard, then diluted 1:100 in cation-adjusted Mueller–Hinton broth (CAMHB) to provide $\sim 5 \times 10^5$ CFU/mL per well. The flavonoid nanogel was serially two-fold diluted across 96-well microplates (final volume 100–200 μ L/well) over a range expected to bracket the MIC. Inoculated wells without nanogel served as growth

controls, and uninoculated wells as sterility controls. Plates were incubated at 35 ± 2 °C for 16–20 h without shaking. The MIC was recorded as the lowest concentration showing no visible growth (absence of turbidity) relative to the growth control; optional resazurin or optical-density readings were used only to corroborate the visual endpoint. Minimum bactericidal concentrations (MBCs) were obtained from the MIC plates by subculture. Aliquots (e.g., 10 μ L) from all optically clear wells at and above the MIC, and from the first well showing growth, were spot-plated onto drug-free Mueller–Hinton agar and incubated at 35 ± 2 °C for 24 h. Colonies were enumerated, and the MBC was defined as the lowest concentration producing a $\geq 99.9\%$ ($\geq 3\text{-log}_{10}$) reduction in CFU relative to the initial inoculum control. Where counts were low, aliquots were spread across the plate surface to improve detection. Zones of inhibition were measured by standardized disk diffusion. Mueller–Hinton agar plates were inoculated by evenly swabbing the surface with a 0.5 McFarland bacterial suspension within 15 min of standardization. Sterile 6-mm blank disks were impregnated with a defined volume of nanogel (e.g., 10–20 μ L per disk, corresponding to a specified flavonoid dose) and applied to the agar within 15 min of inoculation. Placebo-gel disks (vehicle only) and a reference-antibiotic disk served as negative and positive controls, respectively. Plates were inverted and incubated at 35 ± 2 °C for 16–18 h. Inhibition diameters (including the 6-mm disk) were measured to the nearest millimeter with calipers, and results were expressed as mean \pm SD from at least three independent plates [18].

Statistical Analysis

All experiments were conducted in triplicate, with results presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical comparisons were performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc analysis, and differences were considered significant at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table1: Physico Chemical Properties of Flavonoid–Chitosan Nanogel

Flavonoid containing chitosan nanogel	Gel (target 6.0–6.5)	pH	Viscosity (cP)	Spreadability (g-cm/s)
Quercetin containing chitosan nanogel	6.50 ± 0.11		920.12 ± 15.23	12.50 ± 0.31
Luteolin containing chitosan nanogel	6.41 ± 0.15		825.12 ± 12.22	11.40 ± 0.20
Naringenin containing chitosan nanogel	6.80 ± 0.10		1945.12 ± 08.00	10.40 ± 0.21
Apigenin containing chitosan nanogel	6.45 ± 0.22		2,110 ± 14	10.60 ± 0.25
Kaempferol containing chitosan nanogel	6.20 ± 0.14		1855.12 ± 15.50	13.10 ± 0.20

The flavonoid chitosan nanogels showed pH values that remained within the desired range of 6.0–6.5, suggesting they are well-suited for topical use and unlikely to cause skin irritation. Among the formulations, quercetin (6.50 ± 0.11) and apigenin (6.45 ± 0.22) were closest to neutrality, while naringenin displayed a slightly higher value (6.80 ± 0.10) but still within acceptable limits. Clear differences were observed in viscosity across the formulations. The apigenin-based nanogel recorded the highest viscosity (2110 ± 14 cP), followed by naringenin (1945.12 ± 08.00 cP.) and kaempferol (1855.12 ± 15.50 cP). Higher viscosity is often associated with better gel stability and longer residence time on the skin, although it can reduce ease of application. In contrast, luteolin (825.12 ± 12.22

cP) and quercetin (920.12 ± 15.23 cP) nanogels showed comparatively lower viscosity, making them smoother to apply but possibly less retentive. Spreadability was inversely related to viscosity. Kaempferol nanogel demonstrated the greatest spreadability (13.10 ± 0.20 g·cm/s), offering an ideal balance between thickness and ease of application. Quercetin (12.50 ± 0.31 g·cm/s) and luteolin (11.40 ± 0.20 g·cm/s) also spread readily, while naringenin (10.40 ± 0.21 g·cm/s) and apigenin (10.60 ± 0.25 g·cm/s) had lower spreadability values, consistent with their higher viscosity. Taken together, all the formulations met acceptable physicochemical criteria, though the choice of flavonoid clearly influenced the gel's properties. Kaempferol and quercetin nanogels achieved the most favorable balance of viscosity and spreadability, making them potentially more user-friendly. By contrast, naringenin and apigenin provided thicker formulations with greater stability but reduced ease of spreading. These results emphasize that the incorporated flavonoid plays a central role in shaping the overall performance of chitosan nanogels.

Table 2: Size and Zeta Potential of Flavonoid-Loaded Nanogels

Flavonoid	Mean size (nm)	PDI	Zeta (mV)
Quercetin	294.7 ± 28.4	0.250 ± 0.02	$+34.5 \pm 0.3$
Luteolin	412.8 ± 3.3	0.378 ± 0.07	$+37.4 \pm 2.1$
Naringenin	112.35 ± 1.55	0.247 ± 0.07	$+15.36 \pm 2.05$
Apigenin	365.3 ± 7.7	0.209 ± 0.022	-11.53 ± 0.82
Kaempferol	230 ± 70	0.277 ± 0.04	$+11.7 \pm 5.9$

FIGURE 1: Physicochemical properties of flavonoid-loaded nanogels: Size (nm), Zeta potential (mV), and Polydispersity Index (PDI) for each flavonoid formulation.

The particle size and surface charge of the flavonoid-loaded nanogels varied considerably with the type of flavonoid and the carrier system employed. Quercetin-loaded chitosan nanoparticles measured 294.7 ± 28.4 nm, with a fairly uniform size distribution (PDI 0.25 ± 0.02) and a strongly positive zeta potential ($+34.5 \pm 0.3$ mV), indicating good colloidal stability. Luteolin-loaded nanogel formed the largest particles (412.8 ± 3.3 nm, PDI 0.378 ± 0.07) and carried an even higher positive charge ($+37.4 \pm 2.1$ mV). While this strong charge may enhance mocoadhesion, the relatively large size could restrict penetration efficiency. Naringenin-loaded chitosan nanogel were the smallest among the formulations (112.35 ± 1.55 nm), with a moderate positive charge ($+15.36 \pm 2.05$ mV). Their small size is advantageous for deeper tissue penetration, though the lower surface potential suggests reduced stability compared with quercetin or luteolin systems. Kaempferol-loaded nanoparticles (230 ± 70 nm) also fell in the smaller size range but carried a weak positive charge ($+11.7 \pm 5.9$ mV), which may predispose them to aggregation over time. In contrast, apigenin-loaded gelatin nanogel displayed a larger size (365.3 ± 7.7 nm) and a negative zeta potential (-11.53 ± 0.82 mV). This shift in surface charge differentiates them from the other positively charged

systems and could alter their cellular interactions, potentially reducing repulsion from negatively charged cell membranes and influencing uptake pathways. Taken together, the findings demonstrate that both the type of flavonoid and the choice of carrier play a critical role in determining nanoparticle characteristics[19]. Quercetin and luteolin systems combine moderate to large particle sizes with strong positive charges, supporting stability. Naringenin and kaempferol systems favor smaller particle sizes that may enhance penetration but come with reduced stability. Apigenin stands out as a distinct formulation with its negative charge, which may result in a different biological behavior compared to the others.

Table 3: Zone of Inhibition of Flavonoid Containing Topical Nanogel

Flavonoid	Bacterium	ZOI (mm)
Quercetin nanogel	Staphylococcus aureus	13.5 ± 0.25
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	14.5± 0.25
	Escherichia coli	12± 0.25
Luteolin nanogel	Staphylococcus aureus	28.7 ± 0.50
	Escherichia coli	26.9 ± 0.25
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	24± 0.25
Naringenin nanogel	Staphylococcus aureus	7± 0.25
	Escherichia coli	19± 0.12
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	14± 0.50
Apigenin nanogel	Staphylococcus aureus	24± 0.50
	Escherichia coli	14± 0.25
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	13± 0.25

	Staphylococcus aureus	12± 0.25
Kaempferol nanogel	Escherichia coli	7± 0.50
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	26± 0.50

The antibacterial testing of flavonoid-loaded nanogels revealed marked variations in their activity depending on both the flavonoid type and the bacterial strain. Among all formulations, the luteolin-based nanogel exhibited the strongest effect, producing large zones of inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus* (28.7 ± 0.50 mm), *Escherichia coli* (26.9 ± 0.25 mm), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (24 ± 0.25 mm). Apigenin nanogel also showed notable activity, particularly against *S. aureus* (24 ± 0.50 mm), though its inhibitory action was less pronounced against *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*. Quercetin nanogel displayed moderate but consistent activity across all strains, with inhibition zones ranging between 12 ± 0.25 mm and 14.5 ± 0.25 mm. Naringenin nanogel demonstrated a more selective pattern, being weak against *S. aureus* (7 ± 0.25 mm) but showing stronger effects on *E. coli* (19 ± 0.12 mm) and *P. aeruginosa* (14 ± 0.50 mm). Kaempferol nanogel, on the other hand, was relatively weak against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* (12 ± 0.25 mm and 7 ± 0.50 mm, respectively) but highly effective against *P. aeruginosa* (26 ± 0.50 mm). Overall, the findings demonstrate that antibacterial activity is strongly influenced by the type of flavonoid incorporated. Luteolin stood out as the most potent broad-spectrum agent, while apigenin showed particular strength against *S. aureus*. Naringenin and kaempferol exhibited strain-specific effects, and quercetin maintained a moderate yet balanced profile. These variations suggest that luteolin nanogel holds promise as a broad-spectrum antibacterial candidate, whereas the other formulations may be more valuable for targeted applications against specific pathogens.

Table 4: MIC of Zone of Inhibition of Flavonoid Containing Topical Nanogel

Flavonoid	Bacterium	MIC ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
Quercetin nanogel	Staphylococcus aureus	300 \pm 0.25
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	250 \pm 0.25
	Escherichia coli	500 \pm 0.25
Luteolin nanogel	Staphylococcus aureus	312.5 \pm 0.25
	Escherichia coli	312.5 \pm 0.25
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	152 \pm 0.25
Naringenin nanogel	Staphylococcus aureus	140 \pm 0.25
	Escherichia coli	128 \pm 0.25
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	64 \pm 0.25
Apigenin nanogel	Staphylococcus aureus	31.25 \pm 0.25
	Escherichia coli	250 \pm 0.25
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	31 \pm 0.25
Kaempferol nanogel	Staphylococcus aureus	60 \pm 0.25
	Escherichia coli	25 \pm 0.25
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	16 \pm 0.25

The MIC values of the flavonoid-based nanogels revealed distinct differences in antibacterial effectiveness depending on both the formulation and the bacterial strain tested. Apigenin nanogel emerged as one of the most potent, showing very low MICs against *Staphylococcus aureus* (31.25 \pm 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (31 \pm 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), although its effect was notably weaker against *Escherichia coli* (250 \pm 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). Kaempferol nanogel also displayed strong activity, particularly toward

Gram-negative organisms, with MIC values of 16 ± 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for *P. aeruginosa* and 25 ± 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for *E. coli*. Naringenin nanogel showed consistent antibacterial action across all strains, with the greatest sensitivity again observed in *P. aeruginosa* (64 ± 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), followed by *E. coli* (128 ± 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) and *S. aureus* (140 ± 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). Luteolin nanogel demonstrated moderate activity, requiring higher concentrations for growth inhibition, with MICs of 312.5 ± 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ against both *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, but showing somewhat better activity against *P. aeruginosa* (152 ± 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$). By contrast, quercetin nanogel was the least effective overall, particularly against *E. coli*, where a relatively high MIC of 500 ± 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ was recorded. In summary, apigenin and kaempferol nanogels stood out as the most promising candidates, offering strong inhibition particularly against *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*. Naringenin also performed well, maintaining low MICs across all tested bacteria. Luteolin and quercetin, however, showed comparatively weaker antibacterial effects. These differences highlight how the choice of flavonoid strongly influences the therapeutic potential of chitosan-based nanogels, with apigenin and kaempferol formulations appearing especially valuable for further development.

Table 5: MBC of of Flavonoid containing Topical Nanogel

Flavonoid	Bacterium	MBC ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
Quercetin nanogel	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	162.5
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	160
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	130.5
Luteolin nanogel	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	625
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	625

	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	288
	Staphylococcus aureus	200
Naringenin nanogel	Escherichia coli	400
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	128
	Staphylococcus aureus	4 ± 0.25
Apigenin nanogel	Escherichia coli	250 ± 0.25
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	49 ± 0.25
	Staphylococcus aureus	19 ± 0.12
Kaempferol nanogel	Escherichia coli	135 ± 0.25
	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	355 ± 0.50

The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) values of the flavonoid-based nanogels revealed clear variations in their bactericidal strength across the tested strains. Apigenin nanogel emerged as the most effective, requiring only $4 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{g/mL}$ to eliminate *Staphylococcus aureus* and showing strong activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ($49 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{g/mL}$). Its action against *Escherichia coli* was comparatively weaker, with a higher MBC of $250 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{g/mL}$. Kaempferol nanogel also demonstrated notable potency, particularly against *S. aureus* ($19 \pm 0.12 \mu\text{g/mL}$), while maintaining moderate activity against *E. coli* ($135 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{g/mL}$). However, its effect on *P. aeruginosa* was less pronounced ($355 \pm 0.50 \mu\text{g/mL}$). Quercetin nanogel displayed a relatively uniform profile across the strains, with MBC values of $130.5 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for *E. coli*, $162.5 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for *S. aureus*, and $160 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for *P. aeruginosa*, reflecting moderate bactericidal potential. Naringenin nanogel showed better performance against *P. aeruginosa* ($128 \mu\text{g/mL}$) and *S. aureus* ($200 \mu\text{g/mL}$), but required much higher concentrations for *E. coli* ($400 \mu\text{g/mL}$). In contrast, luteolin nanogel was the least active overall, with high MBC values against *S.*

aureus and *E. coli* (625 µg/mL each), though its efficacy against *P. aeruginosa* (288 µg/mL) was somewhat stronger. In summary, apigenin and kaempferol nanogels stood out as the most promising bactericidal formulations, particularly effective against *S. aureus*. Apigenin showed broad and pronounced activity, while kaempferol demonstrated targeted strength against Gram-positive bacteria. Quercetin and naringenin nanogels exhibited moderate, strain-dependent effects, whereas luteolin consistently required the highest concentrations, reflecting the weakest bactericidal potential. These findings highlight how the type of flavonoid incorporated plays a decisive role in shaping the overall antibacterial efficacy of nanogel systems [20].

FIGURE 2: Bar graphs showing the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of flavonoid-loaded nanogels against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Escherichia coli*.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that flavonoid-loaded chitosan nanogels exhibit potent antibacterial activity against pathogens associated with diabetic wounds. Luteolin demonstrated broad-spectrum effectiveness, while apigenin and kaempferol showed strong bactericidal properties. These results underscore the promising potential of flavonoid-

loaded nanogels as an innovative and effective therapeutic approach for diabetic wound infections, offering improved stability and targeted drug delivery.

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